

LANGUAGE ISSUES IN BEHBUDI

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Annotation: Language is the mirror of the nation. It is a means of telling about the past history of each nation. Our native language has survived to this day with many changes. In this article, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, the father of Turkestan Jadids, discusses language issues and the need to learn other languages.

Key words: theatre, school, neighborhood, literary speech, science, dialect

Mahmudhoja Behbudi, who is honored with the name "Father of Turkistan Jadids", had valuable thoughts in many fields. His scientific-practical work on theater, education, literature and the formation of the worldview of Turkestans have been well studied and are being studied to this day. Behbudi left his opinions not only about theater and printing, but also about language. The article entitled "Language Issues" published in the well-known and popular "Oyna" magazine of that time is especially noteworthy.

In his views on language issues, Behbudi was the first among the intellectuals of Turkestan to support the idea of language unity of the Crimean-Tatar enlightener Ismail Gasprinsky, who was the founder of the Jadidism movement, and he himself promoted it throughout Turkestan. With this, Behbudi, like Gasprinsky, emphasizes that the basis of the unity of Russian Muslims should be the unity of language. After all, he came to the conclusion that the unity of language is "the basis of friendship, kindness, mutual help". At the same time, he approves the development of the language over time, that is, unlike other groups of intellectuals, he does not agree with the idea of removing words from other languages into Uzbek.

"Let's improve Persian and Arabic from our language", this is one of many easy dreams, but impossible to fulfill," writes Behbudi in his article.

He refutes those who put forward this idea as follows: "For example, the respected "Sadoyi Turkestan", which is its supporter, should be called "Turk eli dovushi". For example, school, madrasa, journal, magazine, book - all are Arabic. Nine out of ten of our names are Arabic. Now, are we going to pass the world looking for Turkish names for all these endless things?"

However, in the article, Behbudi suggests saying and writing words that have an alternative in Turkish. The use of Arabic-Persian words as little as possible in the language reflects the need to keep the Uzbek language pure. It proves that sentences borrowed from Arabic and Persian can also be used in the Turkish form: "For example, if you want to say 'ulum', 'funun', 'ulama', 'kuzzot', you can write "sciences, sciences, scientists, judges".

Behbudi was a supporter of preserving the purity of the language and the simple structure of literary speech, understandable to ordinary people.

At the end of the article "Language issue", Behbudi mentions the illiteracy of the mothers of our nation as the main problem and obstacle. According to Behbudi, in order to create a

literary language, first of all, "we must educate our mother and teach language to consciousness. Because our lack of knowledge and language are among us."

With the above thoughts, Mahmudhoja emphasized that the development of the literary language and science depends on the knowledge of our mothers, first of all, he raised the issue of sending more girls to schools and making them literate.

Also, in his views, Behbudi emphasizes the need for Turkestan residents to learn Persian, Arabic, and Russian languages along with Turkish. He expresses these views in the article "Two, not four languages are necessary" in "Oyna" magazine:

"We Turkestans need to know Turkish, Persian and Russian." The reason for Turki, that is, Uzbek, is that the soldiers of Turkestan people speak Uzbek. As for Persian, it is the language of Madrasa and Udoba. In all madrasahs, poetry and religious books are taught in Arabic, but the translations of the teachers are Persian. This rule means that the textbook is Arabic, the teacher is Turkish, and the translation is Persian. Three languages have been used in Turkestan since ancient times.

Through this article, Behbudi emphasizes that Turkestans should learn foreign languages in order to keep up with the times, to be aware of modern science and worldviews. Along with the three languages that have existed in Turkestan for a long time, he also calls for learning the Russian language:

"We need to learn Russian for our own benefit and study in government schools. Let us serve our country and our religion. Let's make progress as Muslims. Today's business, industry and country affairs, even the religion of Islam and service to the nation cannot be without knowledge.

In conclusion, today we need editors and repeaters of four languages, that is, Arabic, Russian, Turkish and Persian.

Behbudi also cited a hadith about the necessity of learning foreign languages (Sahih Bukhari, vol. 4, page 156).

In short, Behbudi is embodied as a linguist, sociologist, linguist, ethnographer who has been effective in the development of the nation, the development of science, as well as the formation of the Uzbek language as a literary language.

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